

DEVELOPMENT OF SOME BLOCK LINEAR MULTISTEP METHOD FOR THE NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF LANE–EMDEN TYPE EQUATIONS

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Abstract

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This research paper presents the development of some Block Linear Multistep Methods (BLMM) for the numerical solution of Lane–Emden type equations, which are nonlinear second-order ordinary differential equations with singularities. The proposed methods employ collocation and interpolation techniques based on a power-series approximation. Two block schemes, corresponding to $K=4$ and $K=5$, were derived with uniform orders six and seven, respectively. In obtaining accuracy and efficiency, three classical Lane–Emden problems were solved using two different step sizes of, $h=0.01$ and $h=0.005$. Numerical results show that the method achieves high accuracy, with absolute errors consistently ranging from 10^{-10} to 10^{-12} . The comparison of the results for both step sizes shows that the proposed methods are accurate, stable, and effective for solving this class of singular problems.

Keywords: Block Linear Multistep Methods, Lane–Emden Equation, Collocation and interpolation, Singularity and Stability.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Lane–Emden equation (LEE) is one of the most important models in astrophysics, arising from the study of the thermal and mechanical structure of polytropic stars. The equation, which is nonlinear, second-order, and singular at the origin, is expressed as:

$$y'' + \frac{L}{x}y' + y^n = 0 \quad L > 0 \quad y(x_0) = y_0, \quad y'(x_0) = y_1$$

where y is the dimensionless density, x is the radial coordinate, and n is the polytropic index.

The singularity at $x = 0$ and the nonlinear term y^n make the equation analytically solvable only for specific cases ($n=0,1,5$) as reported by Chandrasekhar (1939). Consequently, efficient numerical methods are essential for obtaining accurate approximations for other values of n ,

A variety of numerical approaches have been employed to solve the Lane–Emden equation. Early techniques such as the Finite Difference Method (FDM) (Henrici, 1962) and the Shooting Method (Lambert, 1973) provided acceptable accuracy but required reformulation into systems of first-order equations which increases computational burden. Runge–Kutta (RK) methods are widely used but tend to lose precision near the singular point. Adomian

Decomposition and Homotopy Perturbation Methods (Rufai & Ramos, 2020) offer semi-analytical solutions, though they often converge slowly and are unsuitable for large domains or high polytropic indices. More recently, collocation and hybrid block methods (Yahaya & Badmus, 2009; Okunuga & Ehigie, 2012; Mansor et al., 2023) have been introduced to improve accuracy and stability by simultaneously computing multiple solution points within a single integration step.

The Block Linear Multistep Method (BLMM) has gained increasing attention as an efficient numerical technique for solving ordinary differential equations. Unlike single-step or predictor–corrector methods that compute one solution per step, BLMMs evaluate several points in a block, thereby improving accuracy, reducing truncation errors, and allowing for parallel computation. Studies by Mohammed (2011) and Badmus (2013) demonstrated the robustness of block schemes for first- and second-order problems, while more recent research by Kolawole et al. (2022) and Yakubu et al. (2017) extended the concept to hybrid and implicit formulations. However, most existing block methods have been restricted to low-order schemes (order ≤ 5), limiting their applicability to singular and highly nonlinear problems such as the Lane–Emden equation.

This paper presents the development of fourth-step ($k = 4$) and fifth-step ($k = 5$) Block Linear Multistep Methods (BLMMs) with uniform orders six and seven, respectively, for the direct numerical solution of Lane–Emden-type equations. The results demonstrated from the proposed BLMMs are accurate, stable, and computationally efficient when applied to nonlinear singular initial value problems. This study therefore contributes a reliable and robust numerical framework for solving Lane–Emden-type equations and similar singular models arising in astrophysical and engineering applications.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

The Lane–Emden equation has been widely studied because of its important role in modeling stellar structure and other astrophysical phenomena. Due to its nonlinear form and the presence of a singularity at the origin, the equation poses significant analytical and numerical challenges. Consequently, several numerical approaches such as collocation methods, spectral techniques, hybrid block methods, and multistep algorithms have been developed to obtain

reliable approximate solutions (Hojjati & Parand, 2011; Parand et al., 2013; Kumar & Singh, 2021; Izadi et al., 2024). Despite these advances, many existing approaches rely on relatively low-order schemes or involve computationally intensive formulations, creating the need for more efficient high-order numerical methods.

The Lane–Emden equation has also been studied using semi-analytical and analytical approximation techniques. Nadeem and Ahmad (2019) applied the Variational Iteration Method (VIM) to obtain approximate analytical solutions of Lane–Emden-type equations with singular initial and boundary conditions. Their method effectively handled the singularity at the origin and produced rapidly convergent series solutions for both linear and nonlinear problems. Numerical examples demonstrated the reliability and computational efficiency of the approach. However, VIM primarily provides analytical approximations and does not yield direct high-order numerical integration schemes. In contrast, the present study focuses on the development of high-order block linear multistep methods that directly compute numerical solutions of Lane–Emden equations through efficient step-by-step integration.

Chandrasekhar (1939) was among the earliest researchers to investigate the Lane–Emden equation in detail, particularly in connection with stellar polytropes and the internal structure of stars. His classical work established the fundamental importance of the equation in astrophysical modeling and emphasized the need for approximate techniques, since analytical solutions are generally unavailable for most parameter values. Nevertheless, the study remained largely analytical and did not provide modern computational algorithms. The present work contributes to this area by introducing practical high-order block methods for approximating solutions of the Lane–Emden equation.

Fatunla (1988) provided a major theoretical foundation for linear multistep methods (LMMs), introducing the fundamental concepts of consistency, zero-stability, and convergence that are widely used in the analysis of numerical schemes. He demonstrated how continuous linear multistep methods can be systematically derived and analyzed while also presenting algorithms for stiff initial value problems. These theoretical developments significantly influenced later research on block and hybrid methods for solving ordinary differential equations (Lambert, 1973; Henrici, 1962; Ramos & Rufai, 2021). However, Fatunla’s work was mainly theoretical and

not specifically developed for singular equations such as the Lane–Emden problem. The present study builds upon this foundation by constructing high-order block linear multistep methods tailored for Lane–Emden-type equations.

Yahaya and Badmus (2009) proposed a **self-starting hybrid block method of order $(4,3,3)^T$** for solving general second-order initial value problems without reducing them to systems of first-order equations. Their method was derived in continuous form, allowing evaluation at both grid and off-grid points for improved derivative approximation. By producing multiple solution points per step, the scheme enhanced computational efficiency and allowed parallel implementation. Numerical comparisons with Fatunla's optimal fourth-order method showed faster convergence and smaller absolute errors. However, the method was limited to relatively low order. The present study extends this direction by developing fourth- and fifth-step block linear multistep methods of orders six and seven, respectively.

Mohammed (2011) developed a continuous linear multistep method for solving first-order ordinary differential equations using a multistep collocation technique. The resulting formulation generated several fourth-order finite difference schemes combined into a block structure. The method was self-starting and produced numerical solutions on non-overlapping intervals without the need for predictors. Stability analysis confirmed the properties of zero-stability, consistency, and convergence, while numerical experiments demonstrated improved accuracy compared to classical Adams–Moulton methods. However, the work was limited to first-order problems, whereas the present study focuses on higher-order schemes applied directly to the second-order Lane–Emden equation.

Okunuga and Ehigie (2012) investigated generalized Lane–Emden-type equations which preserve the singular structure of the original model but include nonlinear source terms of the form $f(x, y)$ instead of y^n . They introduced a Second Derivative Backward Differentiation Formula (SDBDF) derived from continuous multistep collocation schemes to solve these generalized equations. To facilitate computation, they employed a boundary-value approach that first transformed each second-order problem into a **system of first-order equations** before applying their numerical method. This transformation, while effective, increased the number of computations and reduced efficiency. The transformed system was then expressed as a tridiagonal set of nonlinear equations,

enabling stable and accurate computation across the integration domain. Explicit methods were developed for $K=3$ and $K=4$, corresponding to Block Boundary Value Methods (BVM3 and BVM4) of orders four and five, respectively. Although the approach demonstrated good numerical accuracy, it required prior transformation of the equation and remained limited to lower-step formulations.

Yakubu, Yahaya, and Lawal (2017) developed **two-step and four-step block hybrid linear multistep methods** for solving special second-order ordinary differential equations. Using power series collocation, they constructed continuous formulations that were later evaluated at collocation and off-step points. Their analysis showed that the two-step method achieved **uniform order four**, while the four-step method achieved **uniform order six**, with both methods satisfying **consistency, zero-stability, and convergence**. They also demonstrated **$A(\alpha)$ -stability**, making them effective for stiff and non-stiff problems. Numerical experiments demonstrated improved accuracy compared with existing block methods. However, the highest-order scheme remained limited to order six.

Rufai and Ramos (2020) proposed one-step hybrid block Nyström methods for solving second-order singular problems, including Lane–Emden equations. Their approach was specifically designed to address the singularity at the origin, which often leads to numerical instability in standard methods. By combining block formulations with an appropriate starting strategy, they obtained stable and accurate numerical solutions. Related developments in hybrid block and multistep techniques have also been explored to improve the numerical treatment of nonlinear differential equations (Ramos & Rufai, 2021; Kolawole et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the Nyström formulation remained relatively complex and restricted to one-step schemes.

More recently, Mansor, Ismail, Suleiman, and Omar (2023) developed a three-step generalized off-step hybrid block method for solving linear and nonlinear second-order initial value problems. Their approach employed a power series approximation interpolated at initial and off-step points while collocating the second derivative over the interval to construct a continuous scheme. The method achieved high-order accuracy while maintaining consistency and zero-stability. Numerical experiments confirmed its effectiveness for several test problems. However, the study did not address singular equations such as Lane–Emden models. Other recent studies have also

investigated advanced numerical techniques for Lane–Emden and Emden–Fowler equations, including spectral, spline-based, and wavelet-based approaches (Yüzbaşı & Yıldırım, 2022; Saha & Singh, 2024; Ala'yed et al., 2024; Sahoo et al., 2025).

From the literature, it is evident that significant progress has been made in the development of block and hybrid numerical methods for solving singular differential equations. However, many existing schemes remain limited to relatively low-order accuracy or involve fewer computational steps. There is still limited research on higher-step block linear multistep methods applied directly to the Lane–Emden equation. Addressing this gap motivates the present study, which develops a fourth-step block linear multistep method of order six and a fifth-step method of order seven to achieve improved accuracy, stability, and computational efficiency in solving nonlinear Lane–Emden-type equations with singular behavior at the origin.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Derivation of Some K-Step Linear Multistep Methods

Consider the second order ordinary differential equation

$$y'' = f(x, y, y') \quad (3.1)$$

We assume a power series of a single variable x of the form

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{m+t-1} a_j x^j \quad (3.2)$$

as the approximate solution to equation (3.1)

where a_j are the real unknown parameters to be determined and $m+t-1$ is the degree of the polynomial used.

The first and second derivatives of (3.2) are given as;

$$y'(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{m+t-1} j a_j x^{j-1} \quad (3.3)$$

$$y''(x) = \sum_{j=2}^{m+t-1} j(j-1) a_j x^{j-2} \quad (3.4)$$

where

$$f(x, y, y') = \sum_{j=2}^{m+t-1} j(j-1) a_j x^{j-2} \quad (3.5)$$

3.2 Derivation of Hybrid 4th Step BLMM (K=4)

From equation (3.2), $m = 5$, $t = 3$, we have;

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^7 a_j x^j \quad (3.6)$$

The collocation equation is;

$$y''(x) = \sum_{j=2}^7 j(j-1) a_j x^{j-2} = f(x, y, y') \quad (3.7)$$

Equation (3.3) is interpolated at x_{n+j} for $j = 0, \frac{5}{2}, \frac{7}{2}$ and equation (3.4) is collocated at x_{n+j} for $j = 0, 1, 2, 3$ and 4 which give rise to a system of non-linear equations presented in matrix form below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_n & x_n^2 & x_n^3 & x_n^4 & x_n^5 & x_n^6 & x_n^7 \\ 1 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}} & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^2 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^3 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^4 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^5 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^6 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^7 \\ 1 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}} & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^2 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^3 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^4 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^5 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^6 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^7 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_n & 12x_n^2 & 20x_n^3 & 30x_n^4 & 42x_n^5 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+1} & 12x_{n+1}^2 & 20x_{n+1}^3 & 30x_{n+1}^4 & 42x_{n+1}^5 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+2} & 12x_{n+2}^2 & 20x_{n+2}^3 & 30x_{n+2}^4 & 42x_{n+2}^5 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+3} & 12x_{n+3}^2 & 20x_{n+3}^3 & 30x_{n+3}^4 & 42x_{n+3}^5 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+4} & 12x_{n+4}^2 & 20x_{n+4}^3 & 30x_{n+4}^4 & 42x_{n+4}^5 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \\ a_4 \\ a_5 \\ a_6 \\ a_7 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y_n \\ y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\ y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \\ f_n \\ f_{n+1} \\ f_{n+2} \\ f_{n+3} \\ f_{n+4} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

Using Maple Mathematical Software to determine the unknown parameters a_j where $j = 0, (1), 7$ and substituting them into equation (3.6) gives the continuous formulae expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} y(x) = & \alpha_n y_n + \alpha_{n+\frac{5}{2}} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \alpha_{n+\frac{7}{2}} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} + \beta_n h^2 f_n + \beta_{n+1} h^2 f_{n+1} + \beta_{n+2} h^2 f_{n+2} + \beta_{n+3} h^2 f_{n+3} \\ & + \beta_{n+4} h^2 f_{n+4} \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

where α_{n+j} and β_{n+j} are the continuous coefficients to be determined.

Specifically, equation (3.9) is of the form

$$\begin{aligned}
y(x_n) = & \left(1 - \frac{5419}{3360} \frac{x}{h} + \frac{16}{5} \frac{x^3}{h^3} - \frac{10}{3} \frac{x^4}{h^4} + \frac{7}{5} \frac{x^5}{h^5} - \frac{4}{15} \frac{x^6}{h^6} + \frac{2}{105} \frac{x^7}{h^7} \right) y_n + \left(\frac{4459}{960} \frac{x}{h} \right. \\
& - \left. \frac{56}{5} \frac{x^3}{h^3} + \frac{35}{3} \frac{x^4}{h^4} - \frac{49}{10} \frac{x^5}{h^5} + \frac{14}{15} \frac{x^6}{h^6} - \frac{1}{15} \frac{x^7}{h^7} \right) y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \left(-\frac{4075}{1344} \frac{x}{h} \right. \\
& + \left. \frac{8x^3}{h^3} - \frac{25}{3} \frac{x^4}{h^4} + \frac{7}{2} \frac{x^5}{h^5} - \frac{2}{3} \frac{x^6}{h^6} + \frac{1}{21} \frac{x^7}{h^7} \right) y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} + \left(-\frac{19495}{98304} xh + \frac{1}{2} x^2 \right. \\
& - \left. \frac{1777}{2880} \frac{x^3}{h} + \frac{1855}{4608} \frac{x^4}{h^2} - \frac{711}{5120} \frac{x^5}{h^3} + \frac{55}{2304} \frac{x^6}{h^4} - \frac{37}{23040} \frac{x^7}{h^5} \right) f_n \\
& + \left(\frac{6125}{24576} xh - \frac{115}{48} \frac{x^3}{h} + \frac{3259}{1152} \frac{x^4}{h^2} - \frac{1619}{1280} \frac{x^5}{h^3} + \frac{719}{2880} \frac{x^6}{h^4} \right. \\
& - \left. \frac{7}{384} \frac{x^7}{h^5} \right) f_{n+1} + \left(\frac{395185}{147456} xh - \frac{3593}{480} \frac{x^3}{h} + \frac{17677}{2304} \frac{x^4}{h^2} - \frac{24239}{7680} \frac{x^5}{h^3} \right. \\
& + \left. \frac{3401}{5760} \frac{x^6}{h^4} - \frac{479}{11520} \frac{x^7}{h^5} \right) f_{n+2} + \left(\frac{98735}{73728} xh - \frac{2549}{720} \frac{x^3}{h} + \frac{4291}{1152} \frac{x^4}{h^2} \right. \\
& - \left. \frac{6097}{3840} \frac{x^5}{h^3} + \frac{887}{2880} \frac{x^6}{h^4} - \frac{43}{1920} \frac{x^7}{h^5} \right) f_{n+3} + \left(-\frac{4165}{294912} xh + \frac{37}{960} \frac{x^3}{h} \right. \\
& - \left. \frac{209}{4608} \frac{x^4}{h^2} + \frac{347}{15360} \frac{x^5}{h^3} - \frac{61}{11520} \frac{x^6}{h^4} + \frac{11}{23040} \frac{x^7}{h^5} \right) f_{n+4}
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.10}$$

When equation (3.10) is evaluated using non- interpolating point which are $x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}, x_{n+3}$ and x_{n+4} yields the following discrete block scheme

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{n+1} = & \frac{13}{32} y_n + \frac{69}{64} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - \frac{31}{64} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{2887}{98304} h^2 f_n - \frac{8627}{24576} h^2 f_{n+1} \\
& + \frac{12763}{49152} h^2 f_{n+2} + \frac{1815}{8192} h^2 f_{n+3} - \frac{311}{98304} h^2 f_{n+4}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{n+2} = & \frac{17}{80} y_n + \frac{121}{160} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{1}{32} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{1089}{81920} h^2 f_n - \frac{14431}{61440} h^2 f_{n+1} \\
& - \frac{36313}{122880} h^2 f_{n+2} - \frac{647}{61440} h^2 f_{n+3} - \frac{23}{49152} h^2 f_{n+4}
\end{aligned}$$

$$y_{n+3} = \frac{3}{160} y_n + \frac{139}{320} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{35}{64} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{227}{163840} h^2 f_n - \frac{767}{40960} h^2 f_{n+1} \\ - \frac{10411}{245760} h^2 f_{n+2} - \frac{3505}{24576} h^2 f_{n+3} - \frac{953}{491520} h^2 f_{n+4}$$

$$y_{n+4} = -\frac{23}{40} y_n + \frac{121}{80} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{1}{16} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} + \frac{985}{24576} h^2 f_n + \frac{18337}{30720} h^2 f_{n+1} \\ + \frac{70183}{61440} h^2 f_{n+2} + \frac{10707}{10240} h^2 f_{n+3} + \frac{8077}{122880} h^2 f_{n+4}$$

(3.11)

The second derivative of (3.10) is obtained by differentiating the continuous scheme with respect to x and the results are evaluated at the interpolation points $x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}$ and $x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}$ respectively gives

$$f_{n+\frac{5}{2}} = -\frac{1}{8192} \frac{1}{h^2} \left(585 h^2 f_n + 10100 h^2 f_{n+1} + 14358 h^2 f_{n+2} + 6996 h^2 f_{n+3} \right. \\ \left. + 89 h^2 f_{n+4} - 9216 y_n + 32256 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - 23040 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right)$$

$$f_{n+\frac{7}{2}} = \frac{1}{8192} \frac{1}{h^2} \left(1493 h^2 f_n + 22372 h^2 f_{n+1} + 42462 h^2 f_{n+2} + 34244 h^2 f_{n+3} \right. \\ \left. + 1701 h^2 f_{n+4} - 21504 y_n + 75264 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - 53760 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right)$$

(3.12)

And the proposed Main Blocked- Hybrid method the combination of equation (3.11) and (3.12) as follows:

$$y_{n+1} = \frac{13}{32} y_n + \frac{69}{64} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - \frac{31}{64} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{2887}{98304} h^2 f_n - \frac{8627}{24576} h^2 f_{n+1} \\ + \frac{12763}{49152} h^2 f_{n+2} + \frac{1815}{8192} h^2 f_{n+3} - \frac{311}{98304} h^2 f_{n+4}$$

$$y_{n+2} = \frac{17}{80} y_n + \frac{121}{160} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{1}{32} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{1089}{81920} h^2 f_n - \frac{14431}{61440} h^2 f_{n+1} \\ - \frac{36313}{122880} h^2 f_{n+2} - \frac{647}{61440} h^2 f_{n+3} - \frac{23}{49152} h^2 f_{n+4}$$

$$y_{n+3} = \frac{3}{160} y_n + \frac{139}{320} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{35}{64} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{227}{163840} h^2 f_n - \frac{767}{40960} h^2 f_{n+1} \\ - \frac{10411}{245760} h^2 f_{n+2} - \frac{3505}{24576} h^2 f_{n+3} - \frac{953}{491520} h^2 f_{n+4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{n+4} &= -\frac{23}{40}y_n + \frac{121}{80}y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{1}{16}y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} + \frac{985}{24576}h^2f_n + \frac{18337}{30720}h^2f_{n+1} \\
&\quad + \frac{70183}{61440}h^2f_{n+2} + \frac{10707}{10240}h^2f_{n+3} + \frac{8077}{122880}h^2f_{n+4} \\
y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} &= -\frac{65}{3584}h^2f_n - \frac{2525}{8064}h^2f_{n+1} - \frac{2393}{5376}h^2f_{n+2} - \frac{583}{2688}h^2f_{n+3} \\
&\quad - \frac{89}{32256}h^2f_{n+4} - \frac{16}{63}f_{n+\frac{5}{2}}h^2 + \frac{2}{7}y_n + \frac{5}{7}y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \\
y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} &= \frac{1493}{53760}h^2f_n + \frac{799}{1920}h^2f_{n+1} + \frac{1011}{1280}h^2f_{n+2} + \frac{1223}{1920}h^2f_{n+3} + \frac{81}{2560}h^2f_{n+4} \\
&\quad - \frac{16}{105}f_{n+\frac{7}{2}}h^2 - \frac{2}{5}y_n + \frac{7}{5}y_{n+\frac{5}{2}}
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.13}$$

Equation (3.13) are of uniform order 6 with error constants

$$\left[-\frac{163451}{198180864}, \frac{96583}{495452160}, \frac{76981}{990904320}, -\frac{85541}{49545216}, \frac{1025}{96}, -\frac{17927}{288} \right]^T$$

The first derivative of (3.10) is obtained by differentiating the continuous with respect to x and the results are evaluated at all points $x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}, x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}, x_{n+3}, x_{n+\frac{7}{2}},$ and x_{n+4} respectively which gives

$$\begin{aligned}
z_n &= -\frac{1}{10321920} \frac{1}{h} \left(2046975 h^2 f_n - 2572500 h^2 f_{n+1} - 27662950 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad - 13822900 h^2 f_{n+3} + 145775 h^2 f_{n+4} + 16647168 y_n - 47943168 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\
&\quad \left. + 31296000 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{n+1} &= -\frac{1}{10321920} \frac{1}{h} \left(15071 h^2 f_n + 5947564 h^2 f_{n+1} + 16679642 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 6502860 h^2 f_{n+3} - 47537 h^2 f_{n+4} - 1932288 y_n + 17084928 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\
&\quad \left. - 15152640 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{n+2} &= \frac{1}{10321920} \frac{1}{h} \left(350721 h^2 f_n + 6256852 h^2 f_{n+1} + 6381158 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 1336244 h^2 f_{n+3} + 15505 h^2 f_{n+4} - 5637120 y_n + 9408000 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\
&\quad \left. - 3770880 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+\frac{5}{2}} &= \frac{1}{5160960} \frac{1}{h} \left(67025 h^2 f_n + 1172500 h^2 f_{n+1} + 1684550 h^2 f_{n+2} - 837900 h^2 f_{n+3} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - 2975 h^2 f_{n+4} - 1065984 y_n - 1430016 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + 2496000 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+3} &= -\frac{1}{10321920} \frac{1}{h} \left(129759 h^2 f_n + 2048172 h^2 f_{n+1} + 3605210 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 2603468 h^2 f_{n+3} + 67151 h^2 f_{n+4} - 1932288 y_n + 17084928 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\
&\quad \left. - 15152640 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+\frac{7}{2}} &= \frac{1}{5160960} \frac{1}{h} \left(175077 h^2 f_n + 2632868 h^2 f_{n+1} + 5000254 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 5673220 h^2 f_{n+3} + 160181 h^2 f_{n+4} - 2528256 y_n + 3687936 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\
&\quad \left. - 1159680 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+4} &= \frac{1}{10321920} \frac{1}{h} \left(1164289 h^2 f_n + 17252564 h^2 f_{n+1} + 33167974 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 28502964 h^2 f_{n+3} + 3065489 h^2 f_{n+4} - 16647168 y_n + 47943168 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\
&\quad \left. - 31296000 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

Equation (3.14) are of uniform order 6 with error constants

$$\left[\frac{10247125}{288}, -\frac{2747531}{288}, -\frac{278875}{288}, -\frac{1414699}{288}, \frac{1184629}{288}, -\frac{2030903}{288}, -\frac{14918699}{288} \right]^T$$

3.3 Derivation of the Hybrid 5-Step BLMM (K = 5)

From equation (3.2), $m = 6$, $t = 3$, we have;

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^8 a_j x^j \quad (3.15)$$

The collocation equation is;

$$y''(x) = \sum_{j=2}^8 j(j-1)a_j x^{j-2} = f(x, y, y') \quad (3.16)$$

Equation (3.15) is interpolated at x_{n+j} for $j = 0, \frac{5}{2}, \frac{7}{2}$ and equation (3.16) is collocated at x_{n+j} for $j = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$ and 5 which give rise to a system of non-linear equations presented in matrix form below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_n & x_n^2 & x_n^3 & x_n^4 & x_n^5 & x_n^6 & x_n^7 & x_n^8 \\ 1 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}} & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^2 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^3 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^4 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^5 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^6 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^7 & x_{n+\frac{5}{2}}^8 \\ 1 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}} & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^2 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^3 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^4 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^5 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^6 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^7 & x_{n+\frac{7}{2}}^8 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_n & 12x_n^2 & 20x_n^3 & 30x_n^4 & 42x_n^5 & 56x_n^6 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+1} & 12x_{n+1}^2 & 20x_{n+1}^3 & 30x_{n+1}^4 & 42x_{n+1}^5 & 56x_{n+1}^6 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+2} & 12x_{n+2}^2 & 20x_{n+2}^3 & 30x_{n+2}^4 & 42x_{n+2}^5 & 56x_{n+2}^6 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+3} & 12x_{n+3}^2 & 20x_{n+3}^3 & 30x_{n+3}^4 & 42x_{n+3}^5 & 56x_{n+3}^6 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+4} & 12x_{n+4}^2 & 20x_{n+4}^3 & 30x_{n+4}^4 & 42x_{n+4}^5 & 56x_{n+4}^6 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+5} & 12x_{n+5}^2 & 20x_{n+5}^3 & 30x_{n+5}^4 & 42x_{n+5}^5 & 56x_{n+5}^6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \\ a_4 \\ a_5 \\ a_6 \\ a_7 \\ a_8 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y_n \\ y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\ y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \\ f_n \\ f_{n+1} \\ f_{n+2} \\ f_{n+3} \\ f_{n+4} \\ f_{n+5} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.17)$$

The same procedure which we followed for $K=4$ was also applied here to obtain the following Main Blocked-Hybrid method given as follow:

$$y(x) = \alpha_n y_n + \alpha_{n+\frac{5}{2}} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \alpha_{n+\frac{7}{2}} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} + \beta_n h^2 f_n + \beta_{n+1} h^2 f_{n+1} + \beta_{n+2} h^2 f_{n+2} + \beta_{n+3} h^2 f_{n+3} + \beta_{n+4} h^2 f_{n+4} + \beta_{n+5} h^2 f_{n+5} \quad (3.18)$$

Specifically, we have the Proposed Main Blocked- Hybrid method of (3.18):

$$y_{n+1} = \frac{8727}{34055} y_n + \frac{7799}{4865} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - \frac{5853}{6811} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{1912919}{104616960} h^2 f_n$$

$$- \frac{4177949}{20923392} h^2 f_{n+1} + \frac{29891969}{52308480} h^2 f_{n+2} + \frac{21631363}{52308480} h^2 f_{n+3}$$

$$- \frac{1541531}{104616960} h^2 f_{n+4} + \frac{163451}{104616960} h^2 f_{n+5}$$

$$y_{n+2} = \frac{30147}{170275} y_n + \frac{21414}{24325} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - \frac{1954}{34055} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{2791667}{261542400} h^2 f_n$$

$$- \frac{10414897}{52308480} h^2 f_{n+1} - \frac{29007803}{130771200} h^2 f_{n+2} + \frac{4556719}{130771200} h^2 f_{n+3}$$

$$- \frac{837703}{261542400} h^2 f_{n+4} + \frac{96583}{261542400} h^2 f_{n+5}$$

$$y_{n+3} = \frac{787}{170275} y_n + \frac{11769}{24325} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{17421}{34055} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{178649}{523084800} h^2 f_n$$

$$- \frac{467507}{104616960} h^2 f_{n+1} - \frac{3398321}{261542400} h^2 f_{n+2} - \frac{32571347}{261542400} h^2 f_{n+3}$$

$$- \frac{1584341}{523084800} h^2 f_{n+4} + \frac{76981}{523084800} h^2 f_{n+5}$$

$$y_{n+4} = -\frac{8889}{34055} y_n + \frac{2012}{4865} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{5772}{6811} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} + \frac{441449}{26154240} h^2 f_n$$

$$+ \frac{7324879}{26154240} h^2 f_{n+1} + \frac{1280525}{2615424} h^2 f_{n+2} + \frac{8418083}{13077120} h^2 f_{n+3}$$

$$+ \frac{2352677}{26154240} h^2 f_{n+4} - \frac{85541}{26154240} h^2 f_{n+5}$$

$$y_{n+5} = \frac{939}{6811} y_n - \frac{1929}{973} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{19375}{6811} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} - \frac{226775}{20923392} h^2 f_n$$

$$- \frac{2740625}{20923392} h^2 f_{n+1} - \frac{3461375}{10461696} h^2 f_{n+2} + \frac{6047875}{10461696} h^2 f_{n+3}$$

$$+ \frac{23121125}{20923392} h^2 f_{n+4} + \frac{1284475}{20923392} h^2 f_{n+5}$$

$$y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} = -\frac{4475}{258048} h^2 f_n - \frac{247525}{774144} h^2 f_{n+1} - \frac{52307}{129024} h^2 f_{n+2} - \frac{22859}{129024} h^2 f_{n+3}$$

$$- \frac{7261}{774144} h^2 f_{n+4} + \frac{205}{258048} h^2 f_{n+5} - \frac{139}{432} f_{n+\frac{5}{2}} h^2 + \frac{2}{7} y_n + \frac{5}{7} y_{n+\frac{7}{2}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} = & \frac{4753}{184320} h^2 f_n + \frac{15853}{36864} h^2 f_{n+1} + \frac{205571}{276480} h^2 f_{n+2} + \frac{71509}{92160} h^2 f_{n+3} \\
& + \frac{18637}{184320} h^2 f_{n+4} - \frac{2561}{552960} h^2 f_{n+5} - \frac{139}{432} f_{n+\frac{7}{2}} h^2 - \frac{2}{5} y_n + \frac{7}{5} y_{n+\frac{5}{2}}
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.19}$$

The system of equation in (3.19) are of uniform order 7 with error constants

$$\left[-\frac{66276827}{150648422400}, -\frac{52922951}{376621056000}, -\frac{12584917}{753242112000}, \frac{16724261}{37662105600}, -\frac{5934175}{6025936896}, -\frac{7657}{40}, \frac{14607}{40} \right]^T$$

The first derivative of Proposed Blocked- Hybrid method of (3.18) are as followed:

$$\begin{aligned}
z_n = & -\frac{1}{44835840} \frac{1}{h} \left(6814675 h^2 f_n - 39536875 h^2 f_{n+1} - 178587850 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
& - 96017950 h^2 f_{n+3} + 2801575 h^2 f_{n+4} - 292775 h^2 f_{n+5} + 100417536 y_n \\
& \left. - 306625536 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + 206208000 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+1} = & -\frac{1}{1569254400} \frac{1}{h} \left(21781561 h^2 f_n + 1170382655 h^2 f_{n+1} + 3084130978 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
& + 1326240806 h^2 f_{n+3} - 27576011 h^2 f_{n+4} + 2747531 h^2 f_{n+5} - 557531136 y_n \\
& \left. + 3520613376 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - 2963082240 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+2} = & \frac{1}{1569254400} \frac{1}{h} \left(43285031 h^2 f_n + 814188065 h^2 f_{n+1} + 687814558 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
& + 29319706 h^2 f_{n+3} + 12834859 h^2 f_{n+4} - 1414699 h^2 f_{n+5} - 721207296 y_n \\
& \left. + 954971136 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - 233763840 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{n+\frac{5}{2}} &= \frac{1}{156925440} \frac{1}{h} \left(1642325 h^2 f_n + 30248125 h^2 f_{n+1} + 40090250 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad - 32330750 h^2 f_{n+3} + 322625 h^2 f_{n+4} - 55775 h^2 f_{n+5} - 27058176 y_n \\
&\quad \left. - 62221824 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + 89280000 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+3} &= -\frac{1}{1569254400} \frac{1}{h} \left(11323961 h^2 f_n + 196625215 h^2 f_{n+1} + 311697058 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 250247206 h^2 f_{n+3} + 18982709 h^2 f_{n+4} - 1184629 h^2 f_{n+5} - 180043776 y_n \\
&\quad \left. + 2199407616 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - 2019363840 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+\frac{7}{2}} &= \frac{1}{112089600} \frac{1}{h} \left(1744351 h^2 f_n + 29076355 h^2 f_{n+1} + 50700398 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 87565646 h^2 f_{n+3} + 5627699 h^2 f_{n+4} - 290129 h^2 f_{n+5} - 27058176 y_n \\
&\quad \left. - 17385984 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} + 44444160 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+4} &= \frac{1}{1569254400} \frac{1}{h} \left(71178791 h^2 f_n + 1177679905 h^2 f_{n+1} + 2065355678 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 2500206106 h^2 f_{n+3} + 576541739 h^2 f_{n+4} - 14918699 h^2 f_{n+5} - 1098694656 y_n \\
&\quad \left. + 2276176896 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - 1177482240 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right) \\
z_{n+5} &= -\frac{1}{313850880} \frac{1}{h} \left(40060325 h^2 f_n + 624021875 h^2 f_{n+1} + 1174891450 h^2 f_{n+2} \right. \\
&\quad + 716311150 h^2 f_{n+3} - 489157775 h^2 f_{n+4} - 92059825 h^2 f_{n+5} - 594690048 y_n \\
&\quad \left. + 2395266048 y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} - 1800576000 y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \right)
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.20}$$

The system of equation in (3.20) are of uniform order 7 with error constants

$$\left[\frac{21696955}{288}, \frac{693074987}{1440}, \frac{792183083}{1440}, \frac{1621075}{72}, -\frac{331006933}{1440}, \frac{15850177}{360}, \frac{2757157163}{1440}, -\frac{475310365}{288} \right]^T$$

3.4 Analysis of the Order and Error Constants

$$L[y(x); h] = C_0 y(x) + C_1 h y'(x) + \dots + C_q h^q y^{(q)}(x) + \dots \quad (3.4.3)$$

3.4.1 Order of the Method

Let the general form of a linear multistep method (LMM) be expressed as:

$$\sum_{j=0}^k a_j y_{n+j} = h^2 \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j f_{n+j} \quad (3.4.1)$$

Where C_q are constants.

A simple calculation yields the following formulae for the constants C_q in terms of the coefficients α_j, β_j .

We associate the linear difference operator

$$L[y(x); h] = \sum_{j=0}^k (\alpha_j y(x + jh) - h^2 \beta_j y'(x + jh)) = 0 \quad (3.4.2)$$

where $y(x)$ is an arbitrary function, continuously differentiable on $[a, b]$. Expanding the test function $y(x + jh)$ and its second derivative $y''(x + jh)$ as Taylor series about x and collecting terms in (3.4.2) gives

$$C_0 = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \dots + k\alpha_k$$

$$C_1 = \alpha_1 + 2\alpha_2 + 3\alpha_3 + \dots + k\alpha_k$$

$$C_2 = \frac{1}{2!}(\alpha_1 + 2^2\alpha_2 + 3^2\alpha_3 + \dots + k^2\alpha_k) - (\beta_0 + \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \dots + \beta_k)$$

$$C_q = \frac{1}{q!}(\alpha_1 + 2^q\alpha_2 + 3^q\alpha_3 + \dots + k^q\alpha_k) - \frac{1}{(q-2)!}(\beta_1 + 2^{q-2}\beta_2 + \dots + k^{q-2}\beta_k),$$

$$q = 3, 4, \dots \quad (3.4.4)$$

Following Henrici, P[30], we say that the method has order ρ if

$$C_0 = C_1 = C_2 = \dots = C_\rho = C_{\rho+1} = 0, \quad C_{\rho+2} \neq 0 \quad C_{\rho+2} \text{ is then the error constant and}$$

$$C_{\rho+2} h^{\rho+2} + y^{(\rho+2)}(x_n) \text{ the principal local truncated error at the point } x_n. \quad (\text{Badmus, 2013})$$

To investigate the order and error constants of the first member of the proposed block hybrid method of $K=4$;

$$\text{By applying the method (3.3.4) on the first member scheme of (3.13) as } C_0 = -1 + \frac{13}{32} + \frac{69}{64} - \frac{31}{64} = 0$$

$$C_1 = -1 + \frac{345}{128} - \frac{217}{128} = 0$$

$$C_2 = -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1725}{512} - \frac{1519}{512} - \frac{2887}{98304} - \frac{8627}{24576} + \frac{12763}{49152} + \frac{1815}{8192} - \frac{311}{98304} = 0$$

$$C_3 = -\frac{1}{6} + \frac{2875}{1024} - \frac{10633}{3072} - \frac{8627}{24576} + \frac{12763}{24576} + \frac{5445}{8192} - \frac{311}{24576} = 0$$

$$C_4 = -\frac{1}{24} + \frac{14375}{8192} - \frac{74431}{24576} - \frac{8627}{49152} + \frac{12763}{24576} + \frac{16335}{16384} - \frac{311}{12288} = 0$$

$$C_5 = -\frac{1}{120} + \frac{14375}{16384} - \frac{521017}{245760} - \frac{8627}{147456} + \frac{12763}{36864} + \frac{16335}{16384} - \frac{311}{9216} = 0$$

$$C_6 = -\frac{1}{720} + \frac{71875}{196608} - \frac{3647119}{2949120} - \frac{8627}{589824} + \frac{12763}{73728} + \frac{49005}{65536} - \frac{311}{9216} = 0$$

$$C_7 = -\frac{1}{5040} + \frac{359375}{2752512} - \frac{3647119}{5898240} - \frac{8627}{2949120} + \frac{12763}{184320} + \frac{29403}{65536} - \frac{311}{11520} = 0$$

$$C_8 = -\frac{1}{40320} + \frac{1796875}{44040192} - \frac{25529833}{94371840} - \frac{8627}{17694720} + \frac{12763}{552960} + \frac{29403}{131072} - \frac{311}{17280}$$

$$= -\frac{163451}{198180864}$$

From the result, we see that

$$C_0 = C_1 = C_2 = C_3 = C_4 = C_5 = C_6 = C_7 \quad \text{and} \quad C_8 = C_{\rho+2} \neq 0 \quad \text{which } \rho = 6$$

This implies that the scheme is of order 6 and the error constant is $-\frac{163451}{198180864}$

The same procedure was followed to derive the error and order constant of all the other schemes.

3.4.2 Zero Stability of the Method

The scheme in equation (2.13) is represented in matrix form as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -\frac{69}{64} & 0 & \frac{31}{64} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -\frac{121}{160} & 0 & -\frac{1}{32} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \frac{5}{7} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{139}{320} & 1 & -\frac{35}{64} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{7}{5} & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{121}{80} & 0 & -\frac{1}{16} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{n+1} \\ y_{n+2} \\ y_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\ y_{n+3} \\ y_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \\ y_{n+4} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{13}{32} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{17}{80} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{3}{160} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{2}{5} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{23}{40} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{n-3} \\ y_{n-2} \\ y_{n-\frac{3}{2}} \\ y_{n-1} \\ y_{n-\frac{1}{2}} \\ y_n \end{bmatrix} + h^2$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\frac{8627}{24576} & \frac{12763}{49152} & 0 & \frac{1815}{5192} & 0 & -\frac{311}{98304} \\ -\frac{14431}{61440} & -\frac{36313}{122880} & 0 & -\frac{647}{61440} & 0 & -\frac{23}{49152} \\ -\frac{2525}{8064} & -\frac{2393}{5376} & -\frac{16}{63} & -\frac{583}{2688} & 0 & -\frac{89}{32256} \\ -\frac{767}{40960} & -\frac{10411}{245760} & 0 & -\frac{3505}{24576} & 0 & -\frac{953}{491520} \\ \frac{799}{1920} & \frac{1011}{1280} & 0 & \frac{1223}{1920} & -\frac{16}{105} & \frac{81}{2560} \\ \frac{18337}{30720} & \frac{70183}{61440} & 0 & \frac{10707}{10240} & 0 & \frac{8077}{122880} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_{n+1} \\ f_{n+2} \\ f_{n+\frac{5}{2}} \\ f_{n+3} \\ f_{n+\frac{7}{2}} \\ f_{n+4} \end{bmatrix} + h^2$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{2887}{98304} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1089}{81920} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{65}{3584} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{227}{163840} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1493}{53760} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{985}{24576} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_{n-3} \\ f_{n-2} \\ f_{n-\frac{3}{2}} \\ f_{n-1} \\ f_{n-\frac{1}{2}} \\ f_n \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -\frac{69}{64} & 0 & \frac{31}{64} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -\frac{121}{160} & 0 & -\frac{1}{32} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \frac{5}{7} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{139}{320} & 1 & -\frac{35}{64} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{7}{5} & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{121}{80} & 0 & -\frac{1}{16} & 1 \end{bmatrix}; B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{13}{32} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{17}{80} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{3}{160} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{2}{5} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{23}{40} \end{bmatrix};$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{8627}{24576} & \frac{12763}{49152} & 0 & \frac{1815}{5192} & 0 & -\frac{311}{98304} \\ -\frac{14431}{61440} & -\frac{36313}{122880} & 0 & -\frac{647}{61440} & 0 & -\frac{23}{49152} \\ -\frac{2525}{8064} & -\frac{2393}{5376} & -\frac{16}{63} & -\frac{583}{2688} & 0 & -\frac{89}{32256} \\ -\frac{767}{40960} & -\frac{10411}{245760} & 0 & -\frac{3505}{24576} & 0 & -\frac{953}{491520} \\ \frac{799}{1920} & \frac{1011}{1280} & 0 & \frac{1223}{1920} & -\frac{16}{105} & \frac{81}{2560} \\ \frac{18337}{30720} & \frac{70183}{61440} & 0 & \frac{10707}{10240} & 0 & \frac{8077}{122880} \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } D = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{2887}{98304} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1089}{81920} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{65}{3584} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{227}{163840} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1493}{53760} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{985}{24576} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{where } A^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \frac{1}{5} & 0 & -\frac{281}{448} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \frac{2}{5} & 0 & -\frac{57}{224} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & -\frac{5}{14} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{3}{5} & 1 & \frac{53}{448} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{7}{10} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{4}{5} & 0 & -\frac{57}{112} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad A^0 = A^{-1}A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

It implies that

$$A^1 = A^{-1}B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{5}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{3}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{7} \end{bmatrix}$$

The first characteristics polynomial of the block method is given by

$$\rho(\lambda) = \det(\lambda A^0 - A^1) \quad \text{Rauf et al. (2015)}$$

Substituting the A^0 and A^1 into the equation above gives:

$$\rho(\lambda) = \det \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{5}{7} \\ 0 & \lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{3}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda & 0 & 0 & -\frac{2}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \lambda & 0 & -\frac{1}{7} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \lambda + \frac{1}{7} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Rightarrow \left(\lambda + \frac{1}{7}\right)\lambda^5 = 0$$

This will yield $\lambda = 0$ (5 times), $\lambda = -\frac{1}{7}$ which shows that the proposed method is zero stable.

3.4.4 Convergence of the Method

According to Fatunla (1988), a block linear multistep method is convergent if and only if it is both consistency and Zero – stable, since our method is both consistent and zero stable, it is thus convergent.

4.0 Numerical experiment

The following Lane–Emden-type initial value problems are selected to evaluate the performance, accuracy, and stability of the developed $k=4$ and $k=5$ block linear multistep method (BLMM) of uniform

order six and seven respectively. Each problem varies in its structure, degree of singularity, and nonlinearity, providing a suitable test bed for verifying the method's robustness under different conditions.

Problem 1

Lame – Emden type with $L=1$

$$y'' + \frac{1}{x}y' - 4e^{1-2y} = 0$$

$$y(0) = 1, \quad y'(0) = 0$$

No exact Solution

Problem 2

Lame – Emden type with $L=2$

$$y'' + \frac{2}{x}y' + (3 - x^2)y = 0$$

$$y(0) = 1, \quad y'(0) = 0$$

No exact Solution

Problem 3

Lame – Emden type with $L=3$

$$y'' + \frac{3}{x}y' + 8\left(1 - \frac{x^2}{2}\right)y = 0$$

$$y(0) = 1, \quad y'(0) = 0$$

No exact Solution

4.1 Numerical Results

Applying problem 1, 2 and 3 into the derived block schemes in equation (3.13), (3.14), (3.19) and (3.20) respectively, then using maple to solve, we obtain the following results presented in table 1, 2, 3, 4,5 and 6 respectively.

Table 1: Numerical Result of Problem 1 at Method K=4

x	$h = 0.005$	$h = 0.01$	Absolute approximate error
0.1	0.996314422181378	0.996314422183617	2.239×10^{-12}
0.2	0.985175480137181	0.985175480142696	5.515×10^{-12}
0.3	0.966330335533526	0.966330335538914	5.388×10^{-12}
0.4	0.939335872404724	0.939335872412322	7.598×10^{-12}
0.5	0.903522292579877	0.903522292589625	9.748×10^{-12}
0.6	0.857933315101919	0.857933315115787	1.3868×10^{-11}
0.7	0.801230807988178	0.801230808008234	2.0056×10^{-11}
0.8	0.731541508340705	0.731541508369020	2.8315×10^{-11}
0.9	0.646203270956351	0.646203270995878	3.9527×10^{-11}
1.0	0.541324854619143	0.541324854683419	6.4276×10^{-11}

In obtaining solution at $h=0.005$, the iteration were done at 200 times while at $h=0.01$ it was done in 100 times and comparing the solutions at the points.

Table 2: Numerical Result of Problem 1 at method K=5

x	$h = 0.005$	$h = 0.01$	Absolute approximate error
0.1	0.996314422185392	0.996314422182526	2.866×10^{-12}
0.2	0.985175480138236	0.985175480141150	2.914×10^{-12}
0.3	0.966330335533664	0.966330335536246	2.582×10^{-12}
0.4	0.939335872417291	0.939335872407294	9.997×10^{-12}
0.5	0.903522292580106	0.903522292583048	2.942×10^{-12}
0.6	0.857933315112863	0.857933315108168	4.695×10^{-12}
0.7	0.801230808028281	0.801230808000574	2.7707×10^{-11}
0.8	0.731541508420535	0.731541508358731	6.1804×10^{-11}
0.9	0.646203270965831	0.646203270979281	1.345×10^{-11}
1.0	0.541324854678392	0.541324854644567	3.3825×10^{-11}

Table 3 : Numerical Result of Problem 2 at Method K=4

x	$h = 0.005$	$h = 0.01$	Absolute approximate error
0.1	0.990049833748977	0.990049833745803	3.1740×10^{-12}
0.2	0.960789439153741	0.960789439138682	1.50590×10^{-11}
0.3	0.913931185274252	0.913931185252167	2.20850×10^{-11}
0.4	0.852143788969373	0.852143788932308	3.70650×10^{-11}
0.5	0.778800783073392	0.778800783014784	5.86080×10^{-11}
0.6	0.697676326071065	0.697676325992194	7.88710×10^{-11}
0.7	0.612626394183206	0.612626394183206	1.043650×10^{-10}
0.8	0.527292423912815	0.527292424042768	1.299530×10^{-10}
0.9	0.444858066074060	0.444858066225472	1.514120×10^{-10}
1.0	0.367879441176511	0.367879441011433	1.650780×10^{-10}

Table 4: Numerical Result of Problem 2 at Method K=5

x	$h = 0.005$	$h = 0.01$	Absolute approximate error
0.1	0.990049833749936	0.990049833752365	2.4290×10^{-12}
0.2	0.960789439168779	0.960789439153578	1.52010×10^{-11}
0.3	0.913931185308219	0.913931185272968	3.52510×10^{-11}
0.4	0.852143789032361	0.852143788966988	6.53730×10^{-11}
0.5	0.778800783169678	0.778800783071277	9.84010×10^{-11}
0.6	0.697676326203356	0.697676326071768	1.315880×10^{-11}
0.7	0.612626394352294	0.612626394186130	1.661640×10^{-10}
0.8	0.527292424243251	0.527292424047969	1.952820×10^{-10}
0.9	0.444858066449649	0.444858066235020	2.146290×10^{-10}
1.0	0.367879441423435	0.367879441189337	2.340980×10^{-10}

Table 5: Numerical Result of Problem 3 at Method K=4

x	$h = 0.005$	$h=0.01$	Absolute approximate error
0.1	0.995012479199112	0.995012479194354	4.7580×10^{-12}
0.2	0.980198673331693	0.980198673310808	2.08850×10^{-11}
0.3	0.955997481888982	0.955997481841940	4.70420×10^{-11}
0.4	0.923116346491305	0.923116346401767	8.95380×10^{-11}
0.5	0.882496902742916	0.882496902601918	1.409980×10^{-10}
0.6	0.835270211622811	0.835270211430067	$11.927440 \times 10^{-10}$
0.7	0.782704538511948	0.782704538260906	2.510420×10^{-10}
0.8	0.726149037407130	0.726149037095058	3.120720×10^{-10}
0.9	0.666976811268560	0.666976810884018	3.845420×10^{-10}
1.0	0.606530659742753	0.606530659567740	4.641470×10^{-10}

Table 6: Numerical Results of problem 3 at Method K=5

x	$h = 0.005$	$h = 0.01$	Absolute approximate error
0.1	0.995012479193340	0.995012479190135	3.2050×10^{-12}
0.2	0.980198673309611	0.980198673290921	1.8690×10^{-11}
0.3	0.955997481842543	0.955997481796276	4.62670×10^{-11}
0.4	0.923116346404073	0.923116346330817	7.32560×10^{-11}
0.5	0.882496902608071	0.882496902520923	8.71480×10^{-11}
0.6	0.835270211441717	0.835270211339106	1.026110×10^{-10}
0.7	0.782704538280082	0.782704538145938	1.341440×10^{-10}
0.8	0.726149037120004	0.726149036954320	1.656840×10^{-10}
0.9	0.666976810912010	0.666976810728304	1.837060×10^{-10}
1.0	0.606530659770534	0.606530659567740	2.027940×10^{-10}

4.2 Discussion of results

From the numerical results, it is observed that both the $K=4$ and $K=5$ block linear multistep methods produced accurate and stable approximations for all test problems. The accuracy of the proposed scheme is assessed using an approximate error obtained through mesh refinement by comparing the numerical solutions at different step sizes. The error analysis indicates that reducing the step size generally leads to smaller errors, which aligns with the theoretical expectation for methods of uniform order six and seven.

Across all problems, the fifth-step BLMM consistently demonstrated slightly higher accuracy than the fourth-step method. This can be attributed to the additional solution point computed per block, enhancing precision. However, the fourth-step method still achieved competitive performance, making it suitable in cases where computational cost is a consideration.

The absolute approximate errors lies between ranging from 10^{-12} and 10^{-10} , demonstrating that both methods provide high-order approximations. The slight difference in error magnitudes highlights the benefit of higher step multistep formulations, though both schemes meet the requirements for accuracy and reliability in singular initial value problems.

In conclusion, the results validate the effectiveness of both BLMMs for the class of Lane–Emden-type problems considered. The fifth-step method offers superior accuracy, while the fourth-step method remains a viable option where computational efficiency is prioritized.

5.0 Conclusion

This research paper developed some Block Linear Multistep Methods (BLMMs) for the direct numerical solution of Lane–Emden-type equations, employing a collocation and interpolation approach based on power-series approximation. Two block schemes were derived at $K=4$ of uniform order six and $K=5$ of uniform order seven. Numerical experiments on standard Lane–Emden problems demonstrate high accuracy and stability. The fifth-step method yielded slightly better accuracy, while the fourth-step method maintained competitive. The developed BLMMs provide an effective and reliable approximation of some Lane Emden problem that has no exact solutions.

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